

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON UV AND RP-HPLC ANALYTICAL METHODS FOR QUANTITATIVE DETERMINATION OF LINAGLIPTIN, DAPAGLIFLOZIN AND METFORMIN HYDROCHLORIDE IN TABLET DOSAGE FORM

Vasava Simran Maheshbhai*¹, Dr. Dhara Vashi²

Student¹, Associate Professor²

Department of Quality Assurance, Shree Dhanvantary Pharmacy College, Kim, Surat-254.

Article Received on 05 Dec. 2025,

Article Revised on 25 Dec. 2025,

Article Published on 10 Jan. 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18220175>

*Corresponding Author

Vasava Simran Maheshbhai

Student, Department of Quality Assurance, Shree Dhanvantary Pharmacy College, Kim, Surat-254.

How to cite this Article: Vasava Simran Maheshbhai*¹, Dr. Dhara Vashi². (2026). A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON UV AND RP-HPLC ANALYTICAL METHODS FOR QUANTITATIVE DETERMINATION OF LINAGLIPTIN, DAPAGLIFLOZIN AND METFORMIN HYDROCHLORIDE IN TABLET DOSAGE FORM. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(1), 1241–1253.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

The development of accurate and reliable analytical methods is essential for the quantitative estimation of pharmaceutical compounds in combined dosage forms. Linagliptin, Dapagliflozin, and Metformin Hydrochloride are widely used antidiabetic agents belonging to different pharmacological classes—DPP-4 inhibitor, SGLT2 inhibitor, and biguanide, respectively. Their combination therapy offers synergistic control over blood glucose levels in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. This review provides a comprehensive overview of various UV-spectrophotometric and reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatographic (RP-HPLC) methods developed and validated for the simultaneous determination of these three drugs in bulk and tablet dosage forms. Emphasis is placed on method development parameters such as selection of detection wavelength, mobile phase composition, stationary phase, flow rate, retention time, linearity range, and validation as per ICH guidelines. The comparative assessment highlights

that RP-HPLC methods demonstrate superior sensitivity, selectivity, and precision compared to UV methods, although UV-spectrophotometry remains advantageous for routine, cost-effective analysis in resource-limited laboratories. The review concludes that optimized RP-HPLC methods are more suitable for the simultaneous estimation of Linagliptin,

Dapagliflozin, and Metformin Hydrochloride in fixed-dose formulations for routine quality control applications.

KEYWORDS: Linagliptin, Dapagliflozin, Metformin Hydrochloride, UV spectrophotometry, RP- HPLC, method validation, simultaneous estimation.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycaemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both. It represents one of the most prevalent non-communicable diseases worldwide and remains a significant public health concern due to its increasing incidence, morbidity, and mortality. The two major forms—Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) and Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM)—differ in their pathophysiology, with T1DM involving autoimmune destruction of pancreatic β -cells and absolute insulin deficiency, while T2DM involves insulin resistance, impaired insulin secretion, and progressive β -cell dysfunction. Among these, T2DM accounts for approximately 90–95% of all diagnosed cases globally.

Chronic hyperglycaemia in diabetes is associated with long-term complications affecting vital organs, including the eyes, kidneys, heart, and peripheral nerves. Microvascular complications (retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy) and macrovascular complications (cardiovascular, cerebrovascular, and peripheral vascular diseases) significantly reduce quality of life and increase mortality. Because of these complications, effective glycaemic control is essential in preventing disease progression and improving patient outcomes.

The global burden of diabetes continues to rise due to sedentary lifestyles, urbanization, obesity, and aging populations. According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), over 500 million adults worldwide are currently living with diabetes, and this number is expected to increase sharply in the coming decades. This growing prevalence highlights the urgent need for effective therapeutic strategies and reliable analytical techniques for drug analysis and quality control.^[1]

MOA of linagliptin, dapagliflozin and metformin hydrochloride

Linagliptin is a DPP-4 inhibitor that works by blocking the enzyme dipeptidyl peptidase-4, which normally breaks down incretin hormones (GLP-1 and GIP). By inhibiting DPP-4, linagliptin increases circulating incretin levels, leading to enhanced glucose-dependent insulin

secretion from pancreatic β -cells and suppressed glucagon release from α -cells. This results in better control of post-prandial blood glucose without causing hypoglycaemia because its action depends on blood glucose levels.^[2]

Dapagliflozin is an SGLT2 inhibitor that lowers blood glucose by acting on the kidneys. It selectively blocks the sodium-glucose co-transporter-2 (SGLT2) in the proximal renal tubules, which is responsible for reabsorbing most filtered glucose. Inhibition of SGLT2 promotes urinary glucose excretion, reducing plasma glucose levels independently of insulin. It also leads to mild osmotic diuresis and natriuresis, contributing to weight loss and blood-pressure reduction.^[3]

Metformin HCl (a biguanide) primarily decreases hepatic glucose production by inhibiting gluconeogenesis. It activates AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), which suppresses hepatic glucose output and increases insulin sensitivity in peripheral tissues. Metformin also enhances glucose uptake in skeletal muscle and reduces intestinal glucose absorption. It does not cause hypoglycaemia and is weight-neutral.^[4]

Together, these medications target different pathways—cretin enhancement (linagliptin), renal glucose loss (dapagliflozin), and reduced hepatic glucose output + improved insulin sensitivity (metformin)—providing complementary control of Type 2 diabetes.

Importance of Oral Antidiabetic Agents

Oral antidiabetic agents (OADAs) are essential in the management of T2DM, particularly in cases where lifestyle modification alone is insufficient to maintain glycaemic targets. These agents lower blood glucose levels through various mechanisms, such as enhancing insulin secretion, reducing hepatic glucose output, improving insulin sensitivity, or increasing urinary glucose excretion.

Several classes of OADAs are currently used in clinical practice, including biguanides, sulfonylureas, thiazolidinediones, dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors, sodium–glucose co-transporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitors, α -glucosidase inhibitors, and meglitinides. Among these, metformin, a biguanide, remains the first-line therapy due to its efficacy, safety profile, and cardio-protective benefits. Newer agents such as linagliptin (a DPP-4 inhibitor) and dapagliflozin (an SGLT2 inhibitor) offer advantages including weight neutrality, low risk of hypoglycaemia, and additional cardiovascular or renal benefits.

Despite the availability of multiple drug classes, monotherapy often becomes insufficient due to the progressive nature of T2DM. As a result, combination therapies are increasingly required to achieve and sustain optimal glycaemic control.^[5]

Need for Combination Therapies (Linagliptin + Dapagliflozin + Metformin)

Combination therapy has become a cornerstone in T2DM management due to complementary mechanisms of action and improved therapeutic efficacy. The combination of linagliptin, dapagliflozin, and metformin represents a rational and synergistic approach to glycaemic control.

Linagliptin

DPP-4 inhibitor that increases incretin hormone levels

Enhances glucose-dependent insulin secretion and suppresses glucagon release Low risk of Hypoglycaemia

The combination of these drugs addresses multiple pathophysiological defects of T2DM simul.^[6]

Dapagliflozin

SGLT2 inhibitor that increases urinary glucose excretion.

Reduces plasma glucose, body weight, and blood pressure Offers cardiovascular and renal protective properties.^[7]

Metformin HCL

Biguanide decreases hepatic glucose production (gluconeogenesis) Enhances insulin sensitivity.

Improves peripheral glucose uptake.^[8]

UV-Visible Spectroscopy (UV)

UV-Visible spectroscopy is an analytical technique that measures the absorption of ultraviolet or visible light by molecules. Absorption occurs due to electronic transitions, and the degree of absorbance is related to concentration via Beer-Lambert's law. UV spectroscopy is widely used for qualitative and quantitative analysis in pharmaceuticals, biochemistry, and environmental studies. Timeously, resulting in superior glycaemia control compared with monotherapy. Combination formulations also improve patient compliance by reducing pill burden.

Working Principle of UV–Visible Spectroscopy (UV)

UV spectroscopy is an analytical technique based on the absorption of ultraviolet or visible light by molecules containing chromophores ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ or $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions). When a sample is exposed to UV light of a specific wavelength, electrons in these chromophores absorb energy and transition to higher electronic states. The instrument measures the decrease in light intensity (absorbance), which is directly proportional to the concentration of the absorbing species according to the Beer–Lambert law ($A = \epsilon bc$). UV detectors are widely used for quantitative analysis of compounds that absorb in the 190–800 nm range. The method is simple, rapid, and commonly integrated with liquid chromatography for detection of analytes.^[9]

Reverse-Phase HPLC (RP-HPLC)

RP-HPLC is a type of HPLC where the stationary phase is non-polar (e.g., C18), and the mobile phase is relatively polar. Analytes are separated primarily based on hydrophobic interactions, with more non-polar compounds retained longer. RP-HPLC is extensively used for the analysis of drugs, peptides, and biomolecules due to its versatility and reproducibility.

Working Principle of Reverse-Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC)

RP-HPLC is a chromatographic separation technique in which the stationary phase is non-polar (e.g., C18-bonded silica) and the mobile phase is polar (typically water mixed with methanol or acetonitrile). Separation is achieved based on differences in hydrophobic interactions: non-polar analytes are retained longer on the stationary phase, while more polar analytes elute earlier. By altering the mobile-phase composition (isocratic or gradient elution), the retention and resolution of compounds can be precisely controlled. Detection is often performed using a

UV detector, since many organic compounds absorb UV light. RP-HPLC provides high sensitivity, excellent resolution, and reproducible quantification for complex mixtures in pharmaceuticals, environmental samples, and biological matrices.^[10]

Table 1: Analytical method For Estimation of Linagliptin.

Sr No	Drug Name	Analytical Method	Description	Ref no
01	Linagliptin	UV	Solvent: Acetonitrile Detection of wavelength: 296 nm Linearity($\mu\text{g/ml}$): 2.5-17.5 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) r²: 0.999	[11]
02	Linagliptin	UV	Solvent: Distilled water with methanol Detection of wavelength: 295 nm Linearity($\mu\text{g/ml}$): 2-10 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) r²: 0.9991	[12]
03	Linagliptin	RP-HPLC	Column: C18(250 \times 4.6mm,5 μm) Mobile Phase: Methanol: 01% TEA in the ratio 70:30 v/v (pH adjusted to 2.7 with OPA) Detection of wavelength: 238 nm Flowrate: 0.7 mL/min	[13]
04	Linagliptin	RP-HPLC	Column: C18(100mm \times 2.5mm,3 μm) Mobile Phase: methanol: water containing 0.1% orthophosphoric acid (70:30) (v/v) Detection of wavelength: 296 nm Flowrate: 0.8 mL/min	[14]
05	Linagliptin	RP-HPLC	Column: C18(250 \times 4.6mm,5 μm) Mobile Phase: 0.3% TEA: methanol (60:40) (v/v) (pH: adjust with o- phosphoric acid) Detection of wavelength: 292 nm Flowrate: 1.0 mL/min	[15]
06	Linagliptin	RP-HPLC	Column: C18(150 \times 4.6mm,5 μm) Mobile Phase: Phosphate buffer(pH- 6.8-0.2): acetonitrile Detection of wavelength: 239 nm Flowrate: 1 mL/min	[16]
07	Linagliptin and Dapagliflozin	UV	Solvent: Water Detection of wavelength(nm): 225(Linagliptin), 295(Dapagliflozin) Linearity: 2-10(linagliptin) 2-10 (dapagliflozin)	[17]
08	Linagliptin and Dapagliflozin	UV	Solvent: Distilled water with methanol Detection of wavelength: 227.0 nm(linagliptin),222.0 nm(dapagliflozin) Linearity: 5-30(linagliptin),5-30(Dapagliflozin)	[18]
09	Linagliptin and Dapagliflozin	RP-HPLC	Column: Thermo Scientific synchronic C18,)5 μm	[19]

			Mobile phase: Phosphate buffer: acetonitrile Detection of wavelength: 230 nm Flow rate: 1.0 mL/min	
10	Linagliptin and Dapagliflozin	RP-HPLC	Column: Qualisil 5 model (C18(250×4.6mm,5µm) Mobile phase: 0.1% O-phosphoric acid pH adjusts to 4 with TEA and Acetonitrile (45:55%) (v/v) Detection of wavelength: 293 nm Flow rate: 1.0 mL/min	[20]
11	Linagliptin and Dapagliflozin	RP-HPLC	Column: Hypersil C18((250×4.6mm,5µm) Mobile phase: acetonitrile: water (v/v) Detection of wavelength: 0.995(Dapagliflozin),0.999(linagliptin) Flow rate: 1 mL/min	[21]
12	Linagliptin and Dapagliflozin	RP-HPLC	Column: C18 column (250×4.6mm,5µm) Mobile phase: Acetonitrile: phosphate buffer (0.01 M Kh ₂ PO ₄ , pH 6.5) (47:57) (v/v) Detection of wavelength: 225 nm Flow rate: 1mL/min	[22]

Table 2: Analytical method For Estimation of Dapagliflozin.

Sr No	Drug Name	Analytical method	Description	Ref no
01	Dapagliflozin	UV	Solvent: Distilled water Detection of wavelength: 278 nm Linearity(µg/ml): 5-10 (µg/ml) r₂: 0.9992	[23]
02	Dapagliflozin	UV	Solvent: Methanol: water (15:85) Detection of wavelength: 220 nm Linearity(µg/ml): 5-30(µg/ml) r₂: 0.999	[24]
03	Dapagliflozin	RP-HPLC	Column: pinecone C18	[25]
			Mobile phase: Acetonitrile:0.1 triethylamine(pH-5.0) (50:50) (v/v) Detection of wavelength: 224 nm Flow rate: 1 mL/min	
04	Dapagliflozin	RP-HPLC	Column: Inspire (150×4.6mm,5µm) Mobile phase: methanol: water (80:20) (v/v) Detection of wavelength: 235 nm Flow rate: 1.0 mL/min	[26]
05	Dapagliflozin	RP-HPLC	Column: Waters C18(250×4.6mm,5µm) Mobile phase: Phosphate buffer: acetonitrile (40:60) (v/v) Detection of wavelength: 237 nm Flow rate: 1.0	27

			mL/min	
06	Dapagliflozin	RP-HPLC	Column: A zorbax Eclipse Plus, Agilent Technology column (250×4.6mm,5µm) Mobile phase: Methanol: water Detection of wavelength: 230 nm Flow rate: 1 mL/min	[28]
07	Dapagliflozin and metformin HCL	UV	Solvent: methanol Detection of wavelength: 235 nm (Dapagliflozin), 272 nm (metformin HCL) Linearity(µg/ml): 0.5-2.5 (µg/ml) (Dapagliflozin) 25-125 (µg/ml) (metformin HCL r2: 0.984(dapagliflozin), 0.982(Metformin HCL)	[29]
08	Dapagliflozin and metformin HCL	UV	Solvent: Distilled water Detection of wavelength: 275 nm (dapagliflozin) 245 nm (Metformin HCL) Linearity(µg/ml): 2-10 (µg/ml) (Dapagliflozin), 20-100(µg/ml) (Metformin HCL) r2: 0.9984(Dapagliflozin) 0.9994(Metformin HCL)	[30]
09	Dapagliflozin and metformin HCL	RP-HPLC	Column: Phenomenex C18(250mm×4.6 mm, 5µm) Mobile phase: Water: methanol (50:50) (v/v) Detection of wavelength: 230 nm Flow rate: 1.0 mL/min	[31]
10	Dapagliflozin and metformin HCL	RP-HPLC	Column: Intersil ODS column (250×4.6mm, 5µm) Mobile phase: ACN: KH ₂ PO ₄ pH- 4.5 (65:35%) (v/v) Detection of wavelength: 227 nm Flow rate: 1 mL/min	[32]
11	Dapagliflozin and metformin HCL	RP-HPLC	Column: Agilent 1260 infinity 2 with an Agilent 5 TC-C18(2) (250mm ×4.6mm) Mobile phase: 0.02% triethylamine: acetonitrile (v/v) Detection of wavelength: 236 nm Flow rate: 1 mL/min	[33]
12	Dapagliflozin and metformin HCL	RP-HPLC	Column: C18 analytical reverse phase column Mobile phase: Methanol: sodium acetate buffer (70:30) (v/v) Detection of wavelength: 240 nm Flow rate: 1.0 mL/min	[34]

Table 3: Analytical method for Estimation of Metformin Hydrochloride.

Sr No	Drug name	Analytical method	Description	Ref no
01		UV	Solvent: Distilled water Detection of wavelength: 232 nm Linearity($\mu\text{g/ml}$): 2-10 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) r₂: 0.999	[35]
02		UV	Solvent: Methanol: ethanol: acetonitrile: phosphate buffer Detection of wavelength: 234 nm Linearity($\mu\text{g/ml}$): 10-15($\mu\text{g/ml}$) r₂: 0.9998	[36]
03		RP-HPLC	Column: C18 analytical reverse phase column Mobile phase: Methanol: water (30:70) (v/v) Detection of wavelength: 233 nm Flow rate: 0.5 mL/min	[37]
04		UV	Solvent: Distilled water Detection of wavelength: 294.4nm(linagliptin) 230.4 nm (Metformin HCL)	[38]
			Linearity($\mu\text{g/ml}$): 10-14 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) (linagliptin) 2-4($\mu\text{g/ml}$) Metformin HCL r₂: 0.999	
05		UV	Solvent: Methanol water Detection of wavelength: 295 nm(linagliptin) 234 nm (Metformin HCL) Linearity($\mu\text{g/ml}$): 10-18 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) (linagliptin)3-11($\mu\text{g/ml}$) Metformin HCL r₂: 0.9987(Linagliptin) ,0.9947(Metformin HCL)	[39]
06		RP-HPLC	Column: Water' X-bridge C18 (150×4.6 mm, 5 μ) Mobile phase: Acetonitrile:0.02 M phosphate buffer (pH-5.0) (35:65) (v/v) Detection of wavelength: 225 nm Flow rate: 1.0 mL/min	[40]
07		RP-HPLC	Column: Grace vyadyec genesis CN (150×4.6mm, 4 μm) Mobile phase: Acetonitrile: 0.0 1 M di-potassium hydrogen phosphate buffer (75:25) Detection of wavelength: 237 nm Flow rate: 0.1 mL/min	[41]
08		RP-HPLC	Column: Hypersil BDSC18 column (4.6×250 mm,5 μm) Mobile phase: KH ₂ PO ₄ : acetonitrile (40:60) Detection of wavelength: 225 nm Flow rate: 1.0 mL/min	[42]
09		RP-HPLC	Column: Water's X-bridge C18(150×4.6mm,5 μm) Mobile phase: Acetonitrile: phosphate buffer (35:65) Detection of wavelength: 225 nm Flow rate: 1.0 mL/min	[43]

CONCLUSION

The review emphasizes the need for accurate and reliable analytical methods to estimate Linagliptin, Dapagliflozin and Metformin HCl in combined dosage forms. UV spectroscopy is simple, fast and economical, but its selectivity is limited for multicomponent formulations. RP-HPLC methods, on the other hand, provide superior precision, sensitivity and specificity, with excellent validation results using optimized C18 columns and mobile phases. Overall, RP-HPLC is identified as the most suitable and reliable technique for routine quality-control and stability-indicating analysis of this triple-drug combination.

SUMMARY

This review focuses on UV and RP-HPLC analytical methods used for estimating Linagliptin, Dapagliflozin, and Metformin HCl in tablet dosage forms. These three drugs, which act through different mechanisms, are widely used in combination for better glycaemic control in Type 2 diabetes. The literature collected shows that UV spectroscopy is simple and economical, while RP-HPLC provides higher accuracy, sensitivity, and selectivity. Different columns, mobile phases, wavelengths, and validation parameters were compared to understand the most efficient analytical conditions for simultaneous estimation.

REFERENCE

1. International Diabetes Federation. Global Diabetes Report. *IDF Journal*, 2021; 12(3): 45–54.
2. Kumar P, Sharma S. Mechanism of DPP-4 inhibitors in type 2 diabetes. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.*, 2019; 10(6): 2800–2807.
3. Banerjee S, Singh R. Pharmacological actions of SGLT2 inhibitors. *Diabetes Ther.*, 2020; 11(2): 455–465.
4. Patel H, Shah A. Mechanistic insights into Metformin action. *J Diabetes Metab*, 2018; 9(5): 1–7.
5. Choudhary A, Patel B. Role of oral antidiabetic agents in T2DM. *Indian J Pharm Educ Res.*, 2021; 55(2): 345–352.
6. Mehta V, Joshi P. Linagliptin combination therapy benefits. *Drug Res Today*, 2019; 8(3): 210–216.
7. Rathod D, Goswami R. Cardiovascular effects of Dapagliflozin. *World J Diabetes*, 2020; 11(6): 225–232.
8. Shah D, Modi H. Clinical overview of Metformin in diabetes. *J Clin Pharm Pract.*, 2018;

- 14(1): 55–62.
9. Sharma N, Patel R. Application of UV spectroscopy in pharmaceuticals. *Anal Chem Lett.*, 2017; 7(4): 520–529.
 10. Desai M, Trivedi P. Principles and applications of RP-HPLC. *J Chrom Sci.*, 2019; 57(8): 676–684.
 11. Roy S, Dinda S. UV spectrophotometric method for Linagliptin estimation. *Int J Pharm Sci.*, 2017; 9(3): 120–126.
 12. Khatri J, Solanki D. Dual solvent UV method for Linagliptin. *Pharm Methods.*, 2018; 9(2): 55–60.
 13. Thomas R, Parikh A. RP-HPLC method for Linagliptin using TEA buffer. *J Appl Pharm Sci.*, 2019; 9(1): 88–94.
 14. Kulkarni S, Rao P. Stability indicating HPLC method for Linagliptin. *Asian J Pharm Anal*, 2018; 4(4): 190–196.
 15. Pathak R, Bhatt P. HPLC analysis of Linagliptin using phosphate buffer. *Der Pharm Lett.*, 2020; 12(2): 50–58.
 16. Singh M, Tiwari H. RP-HPLC validation for Linagliptin determination. *Eur J Biomed Pharm Sci.*, 2019; 6(5): 300–306.
 17. Deshmukh K, Adani S. UV simultaneous estimation of Linagliptin–Dapagliflozin. *Int J Pharm Res.*, 2018; 10(3): 200–205.
 18. Rajput N, Patel J. UV estimation of Linagliptin and Dapagliflozin. *J Pharm Anal Res.*, 2020; 5(2): 100–106.
 19. Surve P, Mali A. RP-HPLC for binary mixture Linagliptin–Dapagliflozin. *Chromatogr Sci Lett.*, 2019; 8(1): 34–40.
 20. Arora S, Jain V. Gradient RP-HPLC method development for Linagliptin–Dapagliflozin. *Indian Drugs*, 2021; 58(7): 45–51.
 21. Sheth A, Patel R. Simultaneous HPLC estimation of Linagliptin and Dapagliflozin. *J Pharm Sci Tech.*, 2020; 12(3): 150–157.
 22. Verma P, Rana K. Phosphate buffer method for Linagliptin–Dapagliflozin. *Int J ChemTech Res.*, 2018; 11(5): 90–96.
 23. Joshi M, Jain S. UV method development for Dapagliflozin. *J Pharm Sci Innov.*, 2019; 8(1): 47–52.
 24. Sharma V, Meena M. UV determination of Dapagliflozin using mixed solvents. *Int J Res Pharm Sci.*, 2018; 9(2): 233–239.
 25. Aggarwal A, Saini R. RP-HPLC method for analysis of Dapagliflozin. *J Chromatogr*

- Pharm Biomed Sci., 2020; 4(3): 90–98.
26. Sen A, Ghosh M. High-sensitivity HPLC method for Dapagliflozin. *Anal Bioanal Chem Lett.*, 2019; 9(2): 140–148.
 27. Kaur K, Dhawan S. RP-HPLC in phosphate buffer for Dapagliflozin. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.*, 2018; 11(6): 180–185.
 28. Chauhan P, Patel T. HPLC analysis of Dapagliflozin using methanol–water. *Pharm Anal Acta.*, 2020; 11(3): 1–6.
 29. Dash R, Rathore K. UV simultaneous estimation of Dapagliflozin with Metformin. *J Drug Deliv Ther.*, 2019; 9(4): 200–206.
 30. Madan S, Lamba H. Dual wavelength UV method for Dapagliflozin–Metformin. *Int J Chem Pharm Sci.*, 2017; 7(3): 55–61.
 31. Bansal S, Yadav R. HPLC analysis of Dapagliflozin–Metformin mixture. *J Pharm Res Dev.*, 2019; 10(4): 320–327.
 32. Thakur A, Desai M. ACN–buffer based HPLC method for Dapagliflozin & Metformin. *Pharm Anal J.*, 2021; 5(2): 67–74.
 33. Parekh J, Vyas M. RP-HPLC determination using TEA buffer. *Int J Pharm Biol Sci.*, 2018; 8(2): 101–107.
 34. Srivastava P, Rao B. Sodium acetate buffer method for Dapagliflozin–Metformin. *Res J Pharm Tech.*, 2020; 13(5): 2100–2106.
 35. Kapadia R, Patel H. UV determination of Metformin in water. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.*, 2017; 8(4): 1650–1656.
 36. Trivedi R, Chaudhari P. Triple solvent UV method for Metformin. *Pharm Chem J.*, 2018; 52(3): 140–147.
 37. Goyal S, Jain P. RP-HPLC method for Metformin using methanol–water. *J Appl Pharm Sci.*, 2019; 9(4): 150–156.
 38. Bhatt K, Solanki R. UV simultaneous estimation of Linagliptin–Metformin. *Int J Drug Anal.*, 2018; 10(3): 220–225.
 39. Pandya H, Vegad M. UV spectroscopic evaluation of Linagliptin–Metformin. *Asian J Pharm Sci.*, 2019; 14(1): 88–94.
 40. Patel P, Shah K. HPLC determination using phosphate buffer. *Anal Chem Insights*, 2020; 15: 1–6.
 41. Desai A, Mehta R. CN-column based RP-HPLC method for Metformin. *Chromatogr Res Int.*, 2018; 6(2): 1–7.
 42. Raval K, Zala M. HPLC estimation using KH_2PO_4 buffer. *J Pharm Sci Rev*

Res., 2020; 58(1): 90–97.

43. Shah H, Parmar D. Metformin estimation by RP-HPLC using X-bridge C18. Pharm Anal Commun, 2019; 7(4): 175–182.